

IOT BASED THEFT DETERRENT FLOORING SYSTEM

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Abstract

There is an exponential increase in cases of larceny and burglary in recent times, as people fail to access proper installation of security system in their personal and workspace. So, we have proposed a IoT based Theft Deterrent Flooring System, which provides a one stop solution for this problem. This system provides the user a good experience of solid security for his or her assets. As it is loaded with features containing many components such as Arduino Uno, piezoelectric sensor, ESP32 Cam module, GSM module and Dc motor integrated together to catch the trespasser. The sensor is a movement based one, as it immediately passes the intruder's movement signal to the embedded Arduino Uno which ESP32 camera module and sends pictures via email. The Gsm module sends alert messages and call to specified phone numbers. After the successful process, the DC motor is switched ON to pump chloroform by using a relay and driver.

Keywords:-Larceny, Piezo sensor, Burglary, Chloroform, Deterrent, Trespasser

I. INTRODUCTION

Advancement in technology has made many important changes throughout the world, which includes the home security system. Traditionally CCTV cameras were the only kind of security system from past decade. This security system has under gone many metamorphoses since the recent years. IoT is the recent technology that has evolved and dominated the world by providing easy access to any technology across the globe. Usage of wireless sensor network in this domain has helped to facilitate low power and low-cost application of this field in a more effective way [13]. Introduction of IoT has led to many innovative applications for the ease life of mankind. Automation is one of the innovative ideas that has been made possible in this era with the help of WSN and IoT. Some examples of automation are home automation system, smart monitoring system etc. The smart home automation also includes many features not just

lighting system but also safety measures like overheating detection, gas leakage detection, fire and smoke detection, electric short circuit detection etc [15][16][18]. This exceptional technology has also resulted in advancement in the arena of security system. Many research and surveys has been going on in this platform for better implementation and use of these security system [8]. Innovation like having biometric scanner, password, security questions and remote operation of door has been made possible [2][10]. Detection of intrusion via an ANDROID application which interprets the alert messages from gsm and also triggers the buzzer to alert about the intrusion [1]. Efficient system has been proposed by making minor changes in the system like using magnetic reed sensor and motion sensor for detection [3][4]. The conventional system has also undergone progress in the software side to make it more dependable like implementation of automated package theft detection, this detects abnormal package pickup behaviour and generates package theft score which can be used as evidence [12]. Another such system was developed which uses door access control to detect forced breach into the home [5]. The proposed project is a smart security flooring system which detect trespassing and alerts the user. This particular framework has already been designed and many further improvements have been made to increase the scope of the system. The flooring system has been made using piezo sensor to detect and raspberry pi as their heart microcontroller along with pi camera which helps to take photos and alerts through email [6]. As further improvement minor changes like PIR sensor for detection and buzzer for alarming has been used in the system [7][17]. Economic flooring system has also been proposed like using Arduino as microcontroller and for perspective images, the system is equipped with servomotor to control the position of the camera [14]. Software development has been for live video surveillance of trespassing which can be accessed around the world [11]. Another such advancement of the system has been made in which Blynk application is used for alerting the proprietor and load cell has been used to detect the approximate weight of the intruder [9]. In this proposed project, we have used piezo sensor of high sensitivity to detect the trespasser. When the sensor detects, the camera immediately captures the images of the intruder and sends it through email. Alert messages and calls are sent to the proprietor and dc motor is switched on to spray chloroform. This system has many technical improvements to capture the intruder. The proposed system is user friendly as it is cost effective, reliable and unobtrusive.

II. Proposed Algorithm

First, In India most of the crime occurs in metropolitan and metro cities which comprises of hypermarket, supermarket, jewellery shops, apartments, villas etc... Traditionally all the places are generally in equipped with CCTV cameras as their only source of security system. Nonetheless the crimes are still taking place in these commercial areas. As a result, the proprietor has to bear loss for his/her assets. The police take days or months to catch those criminals. The main problem here is that we get to know about the crime after it has been committed. This has led to increase in crime rate. To overcome this inevitable situation, we have proposed IOT based Theft Deterrent system. The system build-up is based on detection of uncalled for transit movement of the trespassers under the spear of surveillance area. By this the proprietor can be sans souci about their assets as they are safe. This system captures images, sends alert messages and calls and sprays chloroform to prevent the theft. The system kicks off its working as soon as the piezoelectric sensor achieves the operating range, where pressure applied on to the sensor generates the corresponding voltage as a signal. The output value must be more than 500 to attain the working of the system as lesser signal generation will lead to earlier termination of successive commands. These signals are then received and read by the

Arduino uno microcontroller. The signal is interfaced with ESP32 camera module, GSM module and DC motor consecutively. The ESP32 camera module takes photos and sends alert messages to the user. The GSM module sends calls and messages. As soon as the signal is received by the DC motor, it initializes itself and sprays CHCl_3 on the trespasser immediately. Lastly the string of process winds up.

III. Experiment and Result

3.1. Block Diagram

The figure below shows the functional block diagram of the theft deterrent system.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of IOT based Theft Deterrent system

In this system the Arduino is used as the main microcontroller to interface all other components. The power supply to the circuit is given from a direct AC voltage which is converted into its operating voltage i.e. 5V DC current. The piezo sensor is connected as an analog input which detects the trespassing. After receiving the signal camera module connected takes images and sends via email. The GSM provides output in form of alert messages and calls to the user. The relay switches the functions and also helps to protect the system from high voltage malfunctions. This turns ON the DC motor and with the help of a driver chloroform gets sprayed. The LCD display used here is for demonstration purpose which will not be required in the actual product.

3.2. Architectural Flow of the System

The following figure shows the architectural flow and working of the proposed theft deterrent system which provides highest level of security with innate defence mechanism, hence leads minimal collateral damage.

Fig. 2. Flowchart

3.3. Working And Result

Whenever a trespasser enters and steps on the floor immediately the piezo sensor sense the movement and passes signals to the Arduino microcontroller. The controller sends signals to take images using a ESP32 camera module. Then sends alert messages and call through gsm. These messages and calls are sent to 2-3 users. After successful alarming, the DC motor is switched ON to spray chloroform which is done using relay and driver circuit. This prevents the trespasser to flee from crime site.

Fig. 3. Working

Fig. 4. Output from GSM Module

Fig. 5. Output from ESP32 Camera Module

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed alert system bestows authentic entry, built-in defensive mechanism and comes with sophistication of unobtrusive security to the personal space. The ease of installation beneath the floor tiles and carpets makes it a versatile instrumentation of adoption to the surrounding. The futuristic system will furnish upgradation in alerts to the nearest police stations. By this way we can minimize the collateral damage of the user.

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